

A Future for the World's Last Divided Country

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Abstract: It is such a tragedy that once the same country with the same people, the same ambition, and the same history, the two Koreas have been separated since 1945. One of the most impacted fields from the current divide of both countries is the democratization of the people. Should democratization happen in both countries, it will bring people the rights they did not have before, including voting rights, labor rights, change in culture, and others. One of the comparisons that could be made with the current situation is the German unification in the 1990s. East Germany had a similar situation as North Korea not only politically but also economically before its reunification with West Germany. After its reunification, East Germany managed to achieve its untapped potential, bringing its economy to unprecedented height and giving rights to its people, enabling them to become more blissful. The unification of North and South Korea -- the last divided country in the world -- seems crucial by every conceivable means. But there is one prerequisite for unification: desire. It is a personal belief that the democratization of North Korea will bring out their personal thoughts into actions and more desire for unification and bring peace to both countries.

Entry received on 25 October 2020; accepted 29 November 2020

Keywords: North Korea, South Korea, Korean unification, economic relations between countries, GAEE essay contest

This entry was given the distinction of “First Prize” by the judging panel of the “GAEE Essay Competition on the North Korean Economy” hosted in October 2020 by the Global Association of Economics Education (GAEE) in association with the Youth Forum of North Korea Democratization (YFNKD), and with sponsorship from the Ministry of Unification of the Republic of Korea. For more information about the competition, please visit gace.org. Contact information of the author(s) can be obtained by contacting education@gace.org or seoul.sk@gace.org.

Question Prompt: Discuss the potential impacts of North Korea Democratization on the labor forces, legislation, individual life, culture, and education of its citizen.

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The democratization of North Korean people brings what is essential in human nature to achieve: freedom. They would have access to voting rights, labor rights, and rights

to do the business of what they wish. One society must prosper, take into consideration of members of the community. This points the organization in the direction where most of the society members would be happy. The current structure of North Korea does not offer that aspect, and it is showing that people lack their fundamental rights and lose the capability to think for themselves. Some of the fundamental rights, such as labor rights, are necessary to ensure they do not suffer from overworking while underpaid. It is a right that each worker must-have, and with the democratization of people, they can claim those rights and exercise their rights either by cutting their work hours or getting compensated for the amount of work they do. Voting rights ensure they select policies or the direction the society will head to, which is for the prosperity of the country and people's happiness. Currently, the central government chooses the path with people following it. The direction set may be for the best of the people, but it may not be the case. It is the best option to leave that matter to the voting of the people. Democratization can also bring economic prosperity to society. With freedom, they can do a business of their wish, bringing out more creativity and efforts, with the mind that they will be compensated for what they work for.

East Germany had a similar situation as North Korea both economically and politically before its reunification with West Germany. After its reunification, East Germany managed to bring its potential to the highest point, giving people the rights and prospering economically in the end. Like East Germany before their unification, North Korea is currently dictated by a single leader, Kim Jong Un. Even though dictatorship in North

Korea has some devastating effects on their economy now, it also means that there is a massive potential for North Korea to bring prosperity to the people in terms of blissfulness and economic success as East Germany did. To do so, North Korea should follow the path that East Germany endured to take:

1. North Korea and South Korea should work together to reunite as one country.
2. North Korea and South Korea should negotiate to fill each other's weaknesses and boost each other's strengths.
3. North Korean society must go through democratization, and South Koreans must adjust to unfamiliar social settings.

The only reason that East Germany could prosper was that they were ready to face the changes after reunification and to work collaboratively with West Germany.

In a fully democratized setting, North Korea's most considerable potential is the number of youths willing to work. Because there are many able-bodied youths and a rich number of resources, the possibility of North Korea can surprise the entire World. North Korea's potential seems to become even more significant in the free setting where people decide their future and claim their rights and the control of supply and demand. A good number of youths would also contribute to North Korea's future: young men and women,

who are healthy and passionate, can lead to the bright future of the country with creativity and work ethics.

As the last divided country in the World, the unification of South and North Korea seems crucial by every possible means. But there is one thing necessary for consolidation: desire. It is a personal belief that the democratization of North Korea will bring out their thoughts into actions and bring economic success as well. Through everyone's thoughtful consideration and collaboration, the hope for unification is becoming more feasible day by day. One day, we hope North Korea and South Korea will cross the armistice line and greet each other as their extended lost relatives.

Bibliography

“The Economics of Korean Reunification.” *Worldfinance.com*, 2018,

www.worldfinance.com/special-reports/the-economics-of-korean-reunification.

“The Costs and Benefits of Korean Unification.” *PIIE*, 2 Mar. 2016,

www.piie.com/publications/working-papers/costs-and-benefits-korean-unification.

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The *Archives* is a flagship project led by GAAE with participation from various external partners, including the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs as part of the #SDGAction36897. The *Archives* is hosted courtesy of the Center for Open Science.

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